

PRESENCE OF MACROPLASTIC: ITS EFFECT TO THE ENVIRONMENT OF MAUBUH BEACH PATIKUL, SULU

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ABSTRACT

This research focuses on the effect of macro plastics on the environment of Maubuh Beach. Macro plastics are larger plastic wastes than can be seen with the naked eye. It is becoming an increasingly serious problem in our community. Macro plastic pollution can cause harm to the surrounding area where it is located; it can affect the health of every individual as well as the animal habitat. This study employed survey and interview methods. This study used the mean for data analysis to the effect of macro plastics on the environment of Maubuh Beach. Random sampling was used to select 70 beachgoers to be the research respondents to the effect of macro plastic and 10 local officials to answer the possible interventions to avoid the presence of macro plastic in the environment of Maubuh Beach. A questionnaire and guided question interview are prepared by the researchers and used as the research instruments in this study. The finding shows that macro plastics are the major problem of distraction in the environment of Maubuh Beach. Beachgoers must dispose of their waste in the appropriate receptacle located nearby under the solid waste management policy. By understanding the effects of macro plastics on the environment of Maubuh Beach, local officials may take action about the crisis in waste pollution as soon as possible for future generations, as they need to upgrade garbage disposal systems, have a proper sanitary landfill, implement rules and regulations, form partnerships with relevant parties, and organize regular clean-up drives.

Keywords: *Environment, Effect, Macro plastic, Maubuh Beach*

INTRODUCTION

Maubuh Beach is located in Patikul Sulu, Philippines. There are numerous establishments and beachgoers that can be sources of macro plastics. There is growing concern over the impact of plastics on natural surroundings and the ecosystem. The focus of the study is on macro plastics, which are larger plastic wastes that can be seen with the naked eye. While there has been some research on the movement of small plastics, there is a lack of information on the distribution of macro plastics on beaches, particularly in the upper and middle zones. By reducing the amount of plastic waste that ends up in the ocean, it can minimize the impact on the ecosystem and protect the species that depend on it. The study's findings can inform policymakers and stakeholders about developing effective strategies for managing plastic pollution and promoting sustainable practices.

In aquatic habitats, plastics are becoming an increasingly serious problem, affecting human health as well as the ecosystem. While some research has been done on the general movement of small plastics, observations of large plastics, or micro-plastics, on beaches have not been well documented in the literature. While the majority of studies have concentrated on the movement of plastics along the lower portion of the beach, there has been little research done in the upper and middle zones. This could have an impact on the movement of plastics to the sea, providing information about the origin and source of macro plastics. Here, we sought to provide an overview of the distribution of macro plastics along the sea. First, we examined and discussed the bibliometric analysis of macro plastics on beaches, which offers a framework for managing plastic pollution (Gallitelli, Scalici 2022). Policymakers, corporations, and scientists are placing an increased emphasis on understanding and controlling plastic pollution as a matter of environmental concern (Winton et al., 2020).

Macro plastics may have an impact on the species inside the ecosystem. The effects of climate change are possible. Macro plastics are recyclable and reusable, helping to keep natural habitats undisturbed. Macro plastics are primarily caused by human activities. Hence, a research with regards to this should be conducted as it serves as a way of learning for human and learning is an important aspect in education as uttered by Sabbaha et. al., (2024) cited by Abdulmajid et. al., (2024), Mading et. al., (2024), Balla et. al., (2024) Jarak et. al., (2024) and Sakili et. al., (2024) Indeed, learning is the soul of education that eliminates ignorance within an individual's mind, so even often times, people forget the effects of litter on the environment, surely through a continuous study, there will be people who will be responsible enough when it comes to this kind of matter. Nevertheless, macro-plastic pollution can cause harm to the surrounding area where it is located; it can affect the health of every individual in there as well as the animal habitat. Furthermore, micro- and macro plastics pollution is a growing threat to ecosystem functioning and, consequently, human well-being.

Macro plastics have an impact on the economic environment; they cause the destruction of ecosystems. There are so many people that are affected by this problem because some people cannot control their attitude and always dispose of their plastic waste at sea, which destroys ecosystems. Macro-plastics have an effect on the habitat of aquatic

fisheries; they can destroy their proper home, so we can't see the fish that we had in the past. Plastic can be used again through recycling; people should practice this in order to achieve a better life in this world. Also, people should always practice proper waste disposal because this problem can be avoided by the people themselves.

This study aims to fill the gap by providing an overview of the distribution of macro plastics along the sea, which can help identify the origin and source of macro plastics and inform strategies for managing plastic pollution.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The researchers sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the common macro plastic that can be found in Maubuh beach Patikul Sulu, Philippines?
2. What is the effect of macro plastics to the environment of Maubuh Beach Patikul Sulu Philippines?
3. What are the possible interventions to avoid the presence macro plastic at Maubuh Beach Patikul Sulu Philippines?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Maubuh Beach, which was located in Patikul, Sulu. Its approximate geographical coordinates were 6° 4' North Latitude and 121° 1' East Longitude. The study focused on an area approximately 1 kilometer within the vicinity of Maubuh Beach.

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Sampling Method

The participants of this study are the vendors, local officials and random beach goer of Maubuh Beach Patikul Sulu, Philippines. The researchers selected 70 respondents for random beach goers to answer the survey questionnaire and 10 participants for the vendors and local officials to answer the interview for the total of 80 participants.

In this study, the researchers used Purposive Sampling or Judgement sampling to select the participant of the study. According to Crossman (2020), as cited by Jailani A. et al. (2024), Sasapan et. al. (2024) and Sabbaha et. al. (2024) Purposive Sampling is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study.

Research Instrument

In this study, the researchers used survey questionnaires, interviews, and observations to identify the plastics in Maubuh Beach Patikul Sulu, Philippines. By using a systematic series of questions, questionnaire surveys were a strategy for collecting statistical data about the characteristics, attitudes, or behaviors of a community (Preston 2009) According to EaswarMoorthy and Zarinpoush, an interview was a conversation intended to obtain data. An interviewer conducted a research interview and arranged the interview

process, posed questions, and received answers from the interviewee.

Statistical Treatment of Data

In this research, the researchers used mean and frequency counting. To calculate the mean, each data point in the set was multiplied by a value that was derived from a feature of the input that produced the data point (Carter 2010). According to (Wright 2013) frequency count is the tally of the instances in which you participated in an activity during a given duration.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers submitted a request letter to the Director of Mindanao State University- Sulu Senior High School, seeking permission to conduct the study at Maubuh Beach and to involve at least 70 respondents and 10 participants. Additionally, the researchers reached out to the local officials of Maubuh Beach, requesting the approval to proceed with the research in the area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 Common Macro plastic that can be found in Maubuh Beach Patikul Sulu

Classification	No. of items
Glass	2
Used sacks	2
Metal	4
Used Diapers	9
Plastic bottles	57
Drinking straws	73
Cellophane	81
Plastic cups	113
Others (cigarettes, cloth, plastic spoon, paper plates, etc.)	132

Table 1 illustrates the classifications of macro plastics that can be found in Maubuh Beach, Patikul, Sulu, Philippines. The most abundant classification plastics at Maubuh beach was plastic cups (113) - followed by cellophane (81), drinking straws (73), plastic bottles (57), used diapers (9), metal (4), used sacks (2), and glass (2) and others (132) are the common macro plastics can be found at Maubuh Beach. Plastic has accumulated in the marine environment as a result of modern society's exponential increase in plastic consumption and poor waste management (Gómez et al., 2018). Global beaches and coasts are impacted by this serious environmental problem (Williams et al., 2019). The presence of plastics may raise the us by absorbing chemical contaminants from the substance in the water (Superio, Abreo 2020).

Table 2 Effect of Macro plastic to the environment

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1. Pollution of water.	3.6	.5	Strongly Agree
2. Harms the natural habitat of the sea creatures.	3.6	.6	Strongly Agree
3. Deterioration of environment.	3.5	.5	Strongly Agree
4. Improper sanitary landfills.	3.5	.5	Strongly Agree
5. Destruction an aesthetic appeal of natural setting	3.5	.8	Strongly Agree
6. Destruction of environment.	3.4	.7	Strongly Agree
7. Damage the natural scenery.	3.4	.8	Strongly Agree
8. Increasingly serious danger contamination in the area.	3.4	.7	Strongly Agree
9. Contributing to climate change.	3.2	.7	Agree
10. Global warming.	3.1	.7	Agree
Grand Mean	3.4	.7	Strongly Agree

Legend: (3.26 – 4.00) Strongly Agree, (2.51 – 3.25) Agree, (1.76 – 2.50) Disagree, (1.00 – 1.75) Strongly Disagree.

Table 2 shows the effect of macro plastics to the environment of Maubuh Beach Patikul Sulu. The total mean obtained 3.4 with the verbal description of strongly agree. This means that the respondents strongly agreed to the effects of Maubuh Beach. This implied that macro plastic can negatively affect the environment according to the perceptions of the respondents.

Majority the respondents of this study strongly agree to the following statements that macro plastics can pollute the water, harms the natural habitat of the 9sea creatures, deterioration of environment, improper sanitary landfill, destruction an aesthetic appeal of natural setting, destruction of environment, damage the natural scenery, increase serious danger contamination that macro plastic can affect to the environment of Maubuh beach. Which is related to the study of Pietz et al (2021) that macro plastics are an increasingly common and harmful environmental contaminant that affects both terrestrial and marine systems.

4.3 Interventions to avoid the presence of macroplastics at Maubuh beach Patikul Sulu

Plastics disposal can be separated into legitimate and illicit categories. Different national laws have different definitions of what is and is not legal. Since illicit disposal provides a direct channel to the oceans that the government cannot control, this split in the effect pathway is significant. Alpizar et al. (2020). Moreover, Zhu et al (2018) has stated that plastic pollution is becoming a quickly rising global issue. Environmental awareness and the numerous risks its poser to nature.

Yes, we have an ordinance that posted in this area that throwing any trash in this place is prohibited (LO1, excerpt 1).

This place don't have truck to pick the trash of the beach goes particular in the residents of Maubuh (LO5, excerpt 2).

The conservation of freshwater and marine habitats depends on efforts to lessen the amount of macroplastics found along seashores; at this point, the understanding of possible pollution sources, vectors, and storage is still lacking. Moreover, Winton et al.,(2020) stated for companies, scientists, and policy makers, managing plastic pollution is becoming a top environmental priority. Though freshwater ecosystems are receiving less attention, awareness of the potential harm to the world's seas has increased. Additionally, UNEP (2018) stated plastics end up in the trash because of wasteful manufacture, improper landfill disposal, and poor recycling management.

There are permanent cleaners who clean every day in this area. (LO3, excerpt 3)

There are permanent cleaners in this Beach, including the members of the tanod and BPAT of the barangay. (LO4, excerpt 4)

The legislation that we have is including the signage posted here, also we have an ordinance that throwing trash in this Beach is prohibited (LO2, excerpt 5).

We don't have the place that intended for our waste, because there's no enough space for that in this place (LO4, excerpt 47).

These responses stated that the Maubuh Beach has lack of facilities. Alpizar et al., (2020) has stated that landfills and dumpsites, wastewater treatment, and beneficiation (i.e., recycling or incineration) are the three legal disposal methods. Even with these appropriate disposal methods, leaks may still occur during collection and transit into the maritime environment. Recycling, which focuses on gathering plastic trash to be treated and reused in another way, is a significant component of waste beneficiation.

Conclusions

Overall, the researchers determined the presence of macro plastic in Maubuh beach. Maubuh Beach is one of the top tourist spots in Sulu, it showed few of plastics items that can be found along the shore. The result showed that throwing of plastics will continue if the interventions of different factors will not properly take.

Macro plastics are the major problem in every community not just in the chosen area. It has an impact on the economic environment, it causes the destruction of ecosystems and

the effect of climate change are possible. The respondents strongly agree to the statement that macro plastics can negatively affect the environment of Maubuh Beach. People who lived or visiting the beach should be aware by the cause and effect of plastic to the environment.

Waste management strategies are implemented through policies in the area. The abundance of macro plastic is primarily caused by human activities, only human can manage it well. Although there are still some people who are responsible when it comes to this kind of matter.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, the following are recommended:

1. For local officials they must upgrade garbage disposal systems, Having a proper sanitary landfill. Authorities should consider enhancing the systems for handling waste to lessen the amount of plastic litter that ends up harming our environment could involve better garbage collection, more recycling programs, and advocating for the use of plastic substitutes. Local officials shall have a proper place for macro plastics in the area because, through this initiative, people in the area will have proper waste disposal in order to make the environment clean.
2. For vendors operating at Maubuh Beach should establish and maintain proper sanitary landfills or trash cans for waste disposal. By implementing effective waste management practices, vendors can contribute to maintaining cleanliness and minimizing the presence of macro plastics in the area.
3. For beachgoers. Beachgoers play a significant role in preserving the cleanliness of Maubuh Beach. It is essential for beachgoers to raise their awareness and exercise discipline when disposing of plastic waste. They should refrain from littering and ensure that their plastic waste is properly disposed of in designated bins to prevent environmental degradation.
4. To the residence of the Maubuh beach they need to organize regular clean-up drives. Regular clean-up drives involving local communities can be effective in minimizing the amount of macro plastic at Maubuh Beach. These initiatives not only help to get rid of existing waste but also cultivate a sense of community ownership of the environment.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study used openness to ensure that every participant participated in any data gathering. Also, this study upheld honesty for every result of data in order for us to publish fair research without causing any harm to others. Additionally, we used proper data gathering without forcing the participants to provide ideas about our topic. The researchers ensured to follow those general guidelines to conduct this study. Without any other concerns, this research used sharing ideas with others and socializing with other participants to participate

and give their ideas and suggestions to help us finish this research.

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